

TEXT¹.

- 1 Siddham Gagavi² (puta) Mitayaha jita Anuḷabi
- 2 tumaha kula-sāṭaka . . . vaya-vavi mata[ra]maji-bika-pati Gaga-pavata-
- 3 vihirahi buku-sāḡahaṭa dini me vavi dina puvaya S[iri]naka³-maharajaha
- 4 puta raja M[e]kavaṇa Abayaha cata lagita do avanaka⁴-vasahi
- 5 Vapa-cada puṇamasiya tedasa⁵-paka divas[e] dini

¹ See Plate 22. For Mr. Bell's text, which differs considerably from that given above, see *A. S. C. Seventh Progress Report*, p. 56.

² Here are four letters smaller in size than the other letters of the record. They are written somewhat higher up than the rest of the line and may, therefore, be considered as not belonging to this inscription.

³ Though the letter *ri* is illegible, the reading is beyond doubt. Mr. Bell's text gives the reading *Sirinaka* as quite clear on the stone. Perhaps when he examined the stone forty years ago, the letter *ri* was still legible.

⁴ The letter *na* has been added later below the line.

⁵ May also be read as *te[?]asa*.